

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF FRP PLY SPLICE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

When the FRP structure becomes large, it is required to splice two or more plies to meet the size requirement. In order to understand the mechanical property of the FRP ply splice structure and get strong ply splice structures, the tensile properties of three kinds of unidirectional CFRP ply splice structures have been tested in the previous work in [1]. In this paper, another two structures were designed based on the S1 structure in [1], in order to improve the strength of this type of the ply splice structure. Compared with the S1 structure, the difference of the S1-1 structure was that the spliced point of each ply was optimized to extend the distance between the nearest spliced points. In the S1-2 structure, additional two carbon fiber fabrics were attached on each side of the S1-1 structure to restrain the bending of the specimen under a tensile load to improve the tensile strength. The results show that there is no big difference of the tensile strength between S1 and S1-1 structures, however, S1-2 really performs much higher tensile strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to high strength and low density, fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have been used widely, and FRP structures with large size are required by more and more applications. When the FRP structure becomes large, only one reinforcement ply may not large enough. In the previous work [1], the tensile properties of three kinds of unidirectional CFRP ply splice structures were studied. The results show that, inducing ply splices into CFRP materials, the tensile strength decreases evidently. Due to the ply splice, stress concentrations occur, and the initial fracture happens in the ply splice position, leading to the final fracture on the interfaces between different plies. The interlaminar shear stress and the tensile stress in the through-thickness direction near the ply splice position are the key factors leading to the initial failure. In this paper, some improvements were made based on one of the three ply splice structures, expecting to get higher strength.

2 EXPERIMENTS

Two kinds of CFRP plates with ply splice structures were made through vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) process. As shown in Figure 1, the black line represents the unidirectional carbon fiber fabric, TENAX STS from Saertex GmbH. The matrix was XNR/H6815 epoxy resin from Nagase. Four fabrics were adopted in each kind of specimens. The thickness of all the specimens is about 2 mm. The fiber volume content is about 55%.

The S1 specimen is the structure in [1]. S1-1 was modified from S1. The splice points on the first and the fourth ply were changed, in order to extend the distance between the splice points on the first (or the second) and the third ply (or the fourth). Based on S1-1, additional two carbon fiber fabrics were attached on each side of it, getting S1-2 specimens.

Static tensile tests were performed to evaluate the four joints. The dimensions of the specimens are shown in Figure 2; the length was 250 mm and the width was 10 mm. Two pairs of tabs made with glass fibre-reinforced plastic (GFRP) were used for each specimen to reduce stress concentrations. The length of the tab was 50 mm. The crosshead speed was 1 mm/min. The tensile stress was along the fibre direction. At least four samples were tested to get the average tensile strength.

Figure 1: Sketch of the three ply splice structures

Figure 2: Dimensions of specimens used for tensile strength testing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tensile strength of the structures is shown in Figure 3. The strength of S1-1 structure was 14.2 kN with a standard deviation of 0.57 kN, which was similar with S1 structure. Compared with S1 structure, the strength of S1-2 increased by 21% to 17.4 kN which was about half the strength of the CFRP specimen. The standard deviation was 0.88 kN. Figure 4 shows the typical load-displacement curves for a S1-1 and a S1-2 specimen, exhibiting brittle properties. Figure 5 and 6 show the classical fracture evolution of a S1-1 and a S1-2 structures. For the S1-1 specimen, the initiation fracture happened at about 80.1s, counting from the start of the tension. The initiation fracture of the S1-2 specimen occurred much later, at about 102s.

Figure 3. Tensile strength of different ply splice structures and CFRP plate for 10 mm wide specimens

Figure 4. Typical load–displacement curves for a S1-1 and a S1-2 specimen.

Figure 5. Fracture evolution of S1-1 structure

Figure 6. Fracture evolution of S1-2 structure

Compared with the S1 structure, the difference of S1-1 structure is that the spliced point of each ply is optimized to extend the distance between the nearest spliced points. This modification may have obvious positive effect on reducing the fiber direction tensile stress component of the stress concentration in the vicinity of the spliced point, however, have almost no effect on the other components. The previous work has shown that the tensile stress along the fiber direction is not the key factor deciding the final strength, coinciding with the strength of the S1-1 structure. In the S1-2 structure, additional two carbon fiber fabrics were attached on each side of S1-1 structure to restrain the bending of the specimen under a tensile load to improve the tensile strength. The results show that this modification really can make the structure stronger.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, two structures were designed based on the S1 structure in [1] in order to improve the strength of this type of the ply splice structure. Compared with the S1 structure, the difference of S1-1 structure was that the spliced point of each ply was optimized to extend the distance between the nearest spliced points. In S1-2 structure, additional two carbon fiber fabrics were attached on each side of S1-1 structure to restrain the bending of the specimen under a tensile load to improve the tensile strength. The results show that there is no big difference of the tensile strength between S1 and S1-1 structures, however, S1-2 really performs much higher tensile strength, coinciding with the analysis and conclusions in [1].

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